

Synthesis and structural studies of complexes of 2-nitrobenzaldehyde derived Schiff bases with some bivalent transition metal ions

A. P. Mishra*, Krishna Kumar and L. R. Pandey

Inorganic Research Laboratories, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : apm19@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 20 August 2003, revised 22 August 2005, accepted 29 August 2005

Abstract : Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the Schiff bases 2-nitrobenzylidene-2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline (NDCA) and 2-nitrobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (NACPh) have been synthesized and characterized with the help of microanalytical data, UV-vis, IR, ESR spectroscopy, conductance and magnetic measurements. Ligand field parameters of some of the complexes have also been calculated.

Keywords : Schiff base, bivalent metal complexes, synthesis, structural studies.

Studies of new types of chemotherapeutically important Schiff bases and metal coordinated drugs are now attracting much attention^{1,2}. After suitable structural modifications, the derivatives of such compounds as such may be used as bioactive materials for medicines as well as industry^{3,4}. The aim of this study is to observe the impact of chelation on the therapeutic value of the organic com-

pounds. Some Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes have been synthesized involving the biopotent ligands viz. 2-nitrobenzylidene-2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline (NDCA) and 2-nitrobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (NACPh).

Results and discussion

(a) Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 2-

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic data of the complexes^a

Compd. no.	Molecular and Empirical formula	Colour	Molecular weight		M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. conduc. Λ_M S cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			Obs.	Cal.				
L-I	NDCA	Greenish	360	340.1	176	55	-	-
	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_4$	grey						
01	$[\text{Co}(\text{NDCA})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Yellowish	576	522.0	208	60	38.9	4.20
	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{Cl}_4\text{CoN}_3\text{O}_7$	green						
02	$[\text{Ni}(\text{NDCA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}_2$	Silver	590	523.8	198	55	146.8	Diamag.
	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{Cl}_4\text{NiN}_3\text{O}_7$	grey						
03	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NDCA})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$	Greenish	558	528.6	210	60	24.9	1.93
	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{Cl}_4\text{CuN}_3\text{O}_7$							
L-II	NACPh	Yellow	290	276.6	98	65	-	-
	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{ClO}_3$							
04	$[\text{Co}(\text{NACPh})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	Olive	680	646.1	162	70	42.0	5.09
	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{Cl}_2\text{CoN}_4\text{O}_8$	green						
05	$[\text{Ni}(\text{NACPh})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brown	674	647.9	159	75	33.6	Diamag.
	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{Cl}_2\text{NiN}_4\text{O}_8$							
06	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NACPh})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	Black	60	652.7	175	70	32.3	1.90
	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{Cl}_2\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_8$							

^aAll the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

nitrobenzylidene-2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline (NDCA) :

The complexes show the metal to ligand stoichiometry in 1 : 1 and are air stable. The conductivity values (in $10^{-3} M$ methanol) show the non-electrolytic nature of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} -complexes while the Ni^{II} complex is univalent electrolyte⁵ (Table 1). The weight loss on heating at 100° and 550 °C reflects the thermal stability of complexes (Table 2).

The IR band due to azomethine group in the NDCA ligand (1624 cm^{-1}) has shifted to lower frequency side ($1610 \pm 05 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the spectra of metal complexes due to coordination through azomethine nitrogen⁶⁻⁸. Other main characteristic bands in the ligand remain almost unchanged in complexes, suggesting their non-involvement in chelation. The non-ligand bands due to stretching and rocking vibrations of water appear in the complex spectra at 3450 ± 10 and $750 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The new bands of low intensity in the spectra of complexes around 480 ± 05 and $455 \pm 05 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to M-O and M-N respectively^{7,9}.

The electronic spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NDCA})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex, shows a band at 15910 cm^{-1} (ν_3) assignable to ${}^4A_2-{}^4T_1$ (P) transition. Two more expected bands did not appear clearly and were overlapped. With the help of magnetic moment value (4.20 B.M.), a tetrahedral geometry (Td) has been suggested for this Co^{II} -complex¹⁰⁻¹². The $[\text{Ni}(\text{NDCA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ complex exhibits two bands at 13030 and 18560 cm^{-1} which have tentatively been assigned to ${}^1A_{1g}-{}^1E_g$ (ν_1) and ${}^1A_{1g}-{}^1B_{2g}$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively. Since the Ni^{II} -complex is diamagnetic in nature, hence a square planer geometry (C_{4v}) has been suggested¹⁰⁻¹². The $[\text{Cu}(\text{NDCA})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ complex gives a distorted broad band at 13290 cm^{-1} , corresponding to transition ${}^2E_g-{}^2T_{2g}$. The various ligand field parameters for this complex are as : $10 Dq = 13290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\lambda = (-) 768 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\text{LFSE} = 158.72 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. On the basis of above transitions and parameters an octahedral geometry (Oh) has been suggested for this complex^{12,13}.

(b) Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 2-nitrobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (NACPh) :

The analytical data of the metal complexes indicate metal to ligand (Schiff base) stoichiometry for all the three complexes as 1 : 2. The molar conductance values in methanol ($10^{-3} M$) suggest that the complexes are non-ionic in nature⁵. The complexes are stable against air (O_2) and moisture (H_2O). The values of thermal degradation of complexes at 100° and 550 °C are given in Table 2.

The IR ligand band at 1612 cm^{-1} has shifted to lower side ($1510 \pm 05 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in complexes due to coordination through azomethine nitrogen. A broad band around 3400 cm^{-1} and a sharp band at 1390 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum are assignable to phenolic ν_{OH} stretching and phenolic-OH deformation⁶⁻⁸. These bands have been found absent in the spectra of complexes. An intense band at 1280 cm^{-1} in the ligand due to the phenolic C-O, shifts higher ($1290 \pm 05 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes. These findings suggests the deprotonation of the phenolic-OH after its chelation with metal. A medium intensity band at $745 \pm 05 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_{OH} , rocking) in the spectra of Co^{II} - and Cu^{II} -complexes, are assignable to coordinated water molecules. The new bands of weak intensity at 500 ± 10 and $455 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively.

The $[\text{Co}(\text{NACPh})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex exhibits two bands at 15215 and 20420 cm^{-1} assignable ${}^4T_{1g}(F)-A_{2g}(F)$ and $T_{1g}(F)-T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The value of the magnetic moment for this complex is 5.09 B.M. The ligand field parameters are as : $10 Dq = 8452.77 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 583.51 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.52$, $\lambda = (-) 651 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\text{LFSE} = 100.95 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. These findings are in favour of an octahedral (Oh) geometry¹⁰⁻¹². The $[\text{Ni}(\text{NACPh})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex exhibits two bands at 18420 and 21160 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions ${}^1A_{1g}-{}^1B_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^1A_{1g}-{}^1B_{1g}$ (ν_3) respectively. Since the complex is diamagnetic in nature, therefore a square planar geometry (C_{4v}) has been sug-

Table 2. Thermal decomposition of metal complexes (thermal data)

Complex no.	Metal complexes (Abbr. name)	% Remaining wt., Obs. (calc.)		
		Room temp.	100°C	550°C
01	Co^{II} -NDCA complex	100	93.5 (94.6)	17.2 (15.4)
02	Ni^{II} -NDCA complex	100	99.0 (98.5)	13.9 (14.2)
03	Cu^{II} -NDCA complex	100	99.2 (99.0)	16.8 (15.0)
04	Co^{II} -NACPh complex	100	98.9 (97.5)	14.4 (12.5)
05	Ni^{II} -NACPh complex	100	95.0 (93.3)	13.2 (11.5)
06	Cu^{II} -NACPh complex	100	100 (99.5)	13.9 (12.1)

gested for this complex. The $[\text{Cu}(\text{NACPh})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex gives a band at 15150 cm^{-1} , corresponding to transition ${}^2E_g-{}^2T_{2g}$. The value of various ligand field parameters viz. $10 Dq$, λ and LFSE are as 15150 cm^{-1} , $(-)\ 744\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $180.92\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The band position and parameters favour the geometry to be octahedral (Oh)¹²⁻¹⁴.

¹H NMR studies : (NACPh ligand and its Ni^{II} complex) :

¹H NMR spectrum of the NACPh ligand exhibit the following data (δ ppm) 6.60–7.99 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.62 (1H, s, azomethine) and 9.97 (1H, s, Ar-OH). The assignment based on chemical shift and intensity pattern between ligand and complex have been compared. The coordination induced shifts $\Delta\delta = [\delta(\text{complex}) - \delta(\text{free ligand})]$ or absence of the signals in the vicinity of coordinating functions have been noted^{8,15}. In the spectra of complexes, the signal due to phenolic-OH has been found absent indicating deprotonation of ligand on complexation. Similarly, the signals due to azomethine group associated pattern shift down in complexes, suggesting withdrawal of electron density between C=N on coordination with nitrogen¹⁵. The remaining other signals remain almost unchanged and unshifted in complex spectra.

ESR studies :

The ESR spectrum of the Cu^{II}-NDCA complex has been recorded on an X-band at a frequency of 9.07 GHz at a magnetic field strength of 2000 ± 4000 Gauss at a temperature of 300 K. The spectrum exhibits Lorentzian type of peak^{12,13,16}. The values of ESR parameters viz. g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , G and Δg are as 2.2547, 2.1934, 2.2138, 1.3202 and 0.0613 respectively.

Experimental

All the used chemical and solvents were of AnalaR grade. 2-Amino-4-chlorophenol, 2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline, 2-nitrobenzaldehyde and metal chloride were obtained from Loba chemie, India. Elemental analysis and FT-IR (in KBr) spectra were recorded at SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow. ¹H NMR spectra of only one ligand and its Ni^{II} complex were recorded at Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh. M.p. was determined on a Toshniwal CL-0301 apparatus. Molar conductance (10^{-3} M) was measured by Elico-conductivity bridge at room temperature. Approximate molecular weight has experimentally been determined by Rast method. Magnetic measurement was made by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra (in MeOH) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Lambda-2B-spectrophotometer. The ESR spectra were

recorded at SAIF, IIT Mumbai. Thermal decomposition of complexes have been noted on heating (30 min) in muffle furnace at two temperatures (100° , 550°C) in air.

Synthesis of Schiff bases (ligands) :

The Schiff bases were synthesized by adding the methanolic solution of 2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline/2-amino-4-chlorophenol (0.01 mol) with methanolic solution of 2-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in equimolar ratio. The reaction mixture was then refluxed on a water bath for about 5–7 h. The condensation product was filtered, thoroughly washed with ethanol and ether, re-crystallized with ethanol and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The purity of the synthesized compounds was monitored by TLC using silica gel (yield 55–65%).

Preparation of complexes :

The complexes have been prepared by mixing the methanolic solution of the appropriate metal salt $\text{MCl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}] (0.01 mol) to the methanolic solution of ligand NDCA/NACPh (0.01 or 0.02 mol) in 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 molar ratio, respectively. The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about 7–8 h. A coloured product appeared on standing and cooling the refluxate. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed repeatedly with ether. The complexes were recrystallized twice with ethanol finally washed with diethylether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a dessicator. The complexes were further dried in an electric oven at $50\text{--}70^\circ\text{C}$.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar for laboratory facilities. We are grateful to SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow; IIT Mumbai and Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh for elemental and spectral analyses.

References

1. S. S. Urena and E. Parsons, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 303.
2. V. Casellato and P. A. Vigato, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **23**, 31.
3. T. Hitoshi, N. Tamao, A. Hideyuki, F. Manabu and M. Takayuki, *Polyhedron*, 1977, **16**, 3787; E. M. Hidnot and W. J. Dunn, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 339; T. Jeeworth, M. G. Bhowon and H. Wah, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1999, **24**, 445.
4. U. Sandbhore, S. Padhye, D. Billington, D. Rathbone, S. Franzblau, C. E. Anson and A. K. Powell, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2002, **90**, 127.
5. C. P. Piriz Macoll, *J. Chem. Edu.*, 1951, **36**, 303; W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.

6. N. Saha and K. M. Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 940.
7. A. P. Mishra, V. Shrivastava and S. K. Shrivastava, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 21.
8. R. M. Silverstein, G. C. Bassler and T. C. Morill, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 5th ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1991.
9. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Part A & B, John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1998.
10. A. P. Mishra, M. Khare and S. K. Gautam, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1485.
11. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
12. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, "Elements of Magneto Chemistry", 2nd ed., Affl. East-West Press Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1993.
13. G. Wilkinson, "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", Vol. 3. Main Group and Early Transition Elements, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1987.
14. A. P. Mishra and S. K. Gautam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 324.
15. A. P. Mishra and L. R. Pandey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 94.
16. A. Abragam and B. Bleaney, "EPR of Transition Ions", Clarendon, Oxford, 1970.